

VPLIV UPORABE ORODIJ UMETNE INTELIGENCE, KOT SO OPENAI'S CHATGPT, GEMINI IN BING, NA ZADOVOLJSTVO Z ŽIVLJENJEM MED ŠTUDENTI IZ RAZLIČNIH DRŽAV

Razširjen povzetek:

Namen: Namen članka je raziskati uporabo orodij umetne inteligence (AI) (OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini in Bing) in njihov vpliv na zadovoljstvo z življenjem. Njegov namen je zagotoviti vpogled v to, kako posamezniki uporabljajo orodja AI in kako lahko vplivajo na njihovo splošno dobro počutje.

Cilj: Raziskati uporabo orodij umetne inteligence (AI) (OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini in Bing) in njihov vpliv na zadovoljstvo z življenjem.

Metodologija: Izvedena je bila spletna anketa z uporabo lestvice zadovoljstva z življenjem (SWLS) in dodatnih vprašanj o uporabi orodja AI in demografskih podatkih. Anketo so prevedli v pet jezikov in jo profesorji razdelili študentom in prijateljem. Podatki so bili analizirani s pomočjo IBM SPSS22.

Ugotovitve raziskave: OpenAI ChatGPT je bilo najpogosteje uporabljeno orodje AI (62,1 %), sledita mu Bing (16 %) in Google Bard-Gemini (10,3 %). Več kot 21 % anketirancev je poročalo o izboljšanju zadovoljstva z življenjem po uporabi orodij AI. Večina vprašanih (50,8 %) ni podprla prepovedi orodij AI v šolah.

Znanstvena vrednost: Ta študija zagotavlja prvo obsežno primerjavo uporabe orodja AI in zadovoljstva z življenjem v več državah. Ugotovitve poudarjajo potencialne koristi orodij AI za izboljšanje dobrega počutja.

Praktična vrednost: Študija opredeljuje strategije za posameznike, da povečajo svojo uporabo orodij AI in potencialno povečajo svoje zadovoljstvo z življenjem. Ugotovitve lahko oblikovalce politik obvestijo o tem, kako javnost dojema umetno inteligenco v izobraževanju.

Omejitve raziskave: Omejitve študije vključujejo metodo nenaključnega vzorčenja in možnost pristranskosti samoizbire. Za potrditev ugotovitev so potrebne nadaljnje raziskave z večjimi in bolj raznolikimi vzorci.

Izvirnost: Ta študija je prva te vrste, ki raziskuje razmerje med uporabo orodja AI in zadovoljstvom z življenjem v več državah. Ugotovitve zagotavljajo edinstven vpogled v potencialne koristi umetne inteligence za dobro počutje posameznika.

Naslednji koraki: Izvedite nadaljnje raziskave z večjimi in bolj raznolikimi vzorci, da potrdite ugotovitve. Raziščite specifične vplive različnih orodij AI na različne vidike zadovoljstva z življenjem. Raziščite razloge za oklevanje javnosti glede orodij umetne inteligence in možne koristi umetne inteligence v izobraževanju.

Dodatne opombe: Študija je pilotni projekt in bo v prihodnosti razširjena na več držav. Avtorji verjamejo, da ima članek pomembno praktično vrednost za posameznike in oblikovalce politik.

Gljučne besede: zadovoljstvo z življenjem, Open AI Chat GPT, Gemini, Bing, študenti, izobraževanje.

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THE IMPACT OF USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS, SUCH AS OPENAI'S CHATGPT, GEMINI, AND BING ON LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG STUDENTS FROM VARIOUS COUNTRIES

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Extended summary:

Purpose: The purpose of the article is to investigate the usage of artificial intelligence (AI) tools (OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini, and Bing) and their impact on life satisfaction. It aims to provide insights into how AI tools are being used by individuals and how they may affect their overall well-being.

Objective: To investigate the usage of artificial intelligence (AI) tools (OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini, and Bing) and their impact on life satisfaction.

Methodology: An online survey was conducted using the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) and additional questions about AI tool usage and demographics. The survey was translated into five languages and distributed to students and friends by professors. Data was analyzed using IBM SPSS22.

Research Findings: OpenAI ChatGPT was the most widely used AI tool (62.1%), followed by Bing (16%) and Google Bard-Gemini (10.3%). Over 21% of respondents reported an improvement in their life satisfaction after using AI tools. A majority of respondents (50.8%) did not support a ban on AI tools in schools.

Scientific Value: This study provides the first large-scale comparison of AI tool usage and life satisfaction across multiple countries. The findings highlight the potential benefits of AI tools for improving well-being.

Practical Value: The study identifies strategies for individuals to increase their use of AI tools and potentially enhance their life satisfaction. The findings can inform policymakers about the public's perception of AI in education.

Research Limitations: The study's limitations include the non-random sampling method and the possibility of self-selection bias. Further research with larger and more diverse samples is needed to confirm the findings.

Originality: This study is the first of its kind to investigate the relationship between AI tool usage and life satisfaction across multiple countries. The findings provide unique insights into the potential benefits of AI for individual well-being.

Next Steps: Conduct further research with larger and more diverse samples to confirm the findings. Investigate the specific impacts of different AI tools on various aspects of life satisfaction. Explore the reasons behind public hesitancy towards AI tools and the potential benefits of AI in education.

Additional Notes: The study is a pilot project and will be expanded to include more countries in the future. The authors believe that the article has significant practical value for individuals and policymakers.

Keywords: Life satisfaction, Open AI Chat GPT, Gemini, Bing, students, education.

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Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) tools are rapidly evolving and becoming increasingly integrated into our daily lives. This study delves into the exploration of how these tools, specifically OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini, and Bing, are being utilized by individuals. We investigate the potential impact of AI tool usage on a crucial aspect of well-being - life satisfaction.

The study employs a large-scale survey design, gathering data from participants across multiple countries. This allows us to examine not only the prevalence of AI tool usage but also public perceptions regarding their potential role in educational settings.

This pilot project represents a significant step towards understanding the human dimensions of AI. By analyzing the relationship between AI tool usage and life satisfaction, the study aims to provide valuable insights for individuals, policymakers, educators, and researchers navigating the evolving landscape of AI in society.

This study investigates the relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) tool usage and life satisfaction. We also explore public opinion on AI integration in education.

We aim to answer the research question:

What governmental actions or policies would incentivize individuals to increase their personal usage of the mentioned artificial intelligence tools?

Hypothesis:

H1: More than 50% of respondents have used OpenAI ChatGPT.

H2: More than 50% of respondents have used Gemini.

H3: More than 50% of respondents have used Bing.

H4: More than 50% of respondents using AI tools such as OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini, and Bing experienced improved life satisfaction.

H5: More than 50% of respondents do not support the ban on the use of artificial intelligence in schools, including tools such as OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini, and Bing.

Research field

Artificial intelligence and satisfaction with life

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force across various domains, including healthcare, education, finance, and beyond. Scholars have extensively explored the multifaceted impacts of AI on society, ranging from its implications for decision-making processes to its potential to revolutionize workforce productivity and satisfaction. This literature review synthesizes key findings from recent studies to provide insights into the diverse applications and implications of AI.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming various sectors, including education (Alowais, 2023). While research often emphasizes AI's potential benefits, concerns regarding its impact on human decision-making, laziness, and privacy also exist (Ahmed et al., 2023). This study by Ahmed et al. (2023) investigated these concerns among university students in Pakistan and China, highlighting the need for a balanced approach to AI implementation in education.

AI has the potential to revolutionize healthcare by improving patient care and quality of life (Alowais, 2023). Integrating AI into clinical practice offers significant advancements, but successful implementation requires equipping healthcare providers with the necessary knowledge and tools (Alowais, 2023).

As AI becomes increasingly prevalent, understanding individual attitudes is crucial (Bergdahl, 2023). Bergdahl's (2023) research explores attitudes towards AI through the lens of self-determination theory, focusing on basic psychological needs like autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Their findings suggest that fulfilling these needs is associated with more positive attitudes towards AI (Bergdahl, 2023). This emphasizes the importance of user-centered design when developing and implementing AI solutions.

AI applications in healthcare often involve machine learning (ML) techniques that analyze large amounts of patient data (Challen, 2019). However, concerns exist regarding potential biases within these algorithms, which could impact clinical safety (Challen, 2019). Mitigating bias in AI development and implementation is crucial for ensuring responsible and ethical use in healthcare settings.

Subjective well-being (SWB) is a significant health outcome, and AI can be utilized to identify key factors influencing it (Cruz, 2023). Cruz et al. (2023) analyzed data from over 37,000 older adults across Europe and Israel, identifying the top 50 predictors of SWB using machine learning algorithms. Their findings highlight the importance of social factors, physical health, demographics, and financial status (Cruz et al., 2023). This research demonstrates the potential of AI for understanding and promoting well-being in diverse populations.

Fokas A.S. (2023). Title: Can artificial intelligence reach human thought? - The transformative achievements of deep learning have led several scholars to raise the question of whether artificial intelligence (AI) can reach and then surpass the level of human thought. Here, after addressing methodological problems regarding the possible answer to this question, it is argued that the definition of intelligence proposed by proponents of the AI as “the ability to accomplish complex goals,” is appropriate for machines but does not capture the essence of human thought. After discussing the differences regarding understanding between machines and the brain, as well as the importance of subjective experiences, it is emphasized that most proponents of the eventual superiority of AI ignore the importance of the body proper on the brain, the laterization of the brain, and the vital role of the glia cells. By appealing to the incompleteness theorem of Gödel’s and to the analogous result of Turing regarding computations, it is noted that consciousness is much richer than both mathematics and computations. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, it is stressed that artificial algorithms attempt to mimic only the conscious function of parts of the cerebral cortex, ignoring the fact that, not only every conscious experience is preceded by an unconscious process but also that the passage from the unconscious to consciousness is accompanied by loss of information.

Public perceptions towards AI can influence life satisfaction (Hinks, 2023). Hinks' (2023) study using data from 39 European countries revealed that individuals with negative views on AI reported lower life satisfaction. This highlights the potential for AI-related anxieties and the importance of clear communication about its development and applications. Addressing these concerns through open discussions and responsible policy development can be crucial (Hinks, 2023).

Life satisfaction appears to be influenced by age, following a U-shaped curve (Kaiser, 2022). Kaiser et al. (2022) employed a machine learning approach to analyze data from over 400,000 participants in the German Socio-Economic Panel. Their findings suggest life satisfaction dips around midlife (around 50 years old) before rising again in later years (Kaiser et al., 2022). This research emphasizes the dynamic nature of life satisfaction across the lifespan.

Another study explored the link between life satisfaction, diabetes, and its complications (Kim, 2023). Kim et al. (2023) utilized data from the Korean Longitudinal Study of Aging, analyzing data from over 5,500 participants aged 56 and above. Their findings suggest that life satisfaction (overall, economic, and health-related) is a significant factor influencing the development of comorbid conditions alongside factors like body mass index, income, and age (Kim et al., 2023). This research highlights the potential for interventions promoting well-being to positively impact health outcomes.

While some research focuses on the potential downsides of AI, Lund (2023) explores the possibilities presented by tools like ChatGPT, a large language model from OpenAI. Lund's (2023) paper provides an overview of ChatGPT's technology and explores its potential benefits for academia and libraries, including enhanced search and discovery, reference services, and content creation. The paper also acknowledges the need to address ethical considerations like privacy and bias (Lund, 2023). Further research is needed to explore the responsible integration of AI tools within these critical institutions. Melo A. (2024). Title: ChatGPT: A Pilot Study on a Promising Tool for Mental Health Support in Psychiatric Inpatient Care - This pilot study assesses ChatGPT's effectiveness as an artificial intelligence (AI) chatbot in psychiatric inpatient care. Global mental health challenges highlight a significant treatment gap, mainly due to restricted service access and mental health professional shortages. AI chatbots like ChatGPT offer innovative solutions, providing services such as self-help advice, coaching, psychoeducation, and emotional support.

The concept of AI rights, particularly the right to life, is an emerging area of legal discussion (Milczarek, 2023). Milczarek (2023) explores the criteria for affording entities the right to life, questioning whether advanced AI could potentially qualify for such protection. Further research is needed to address the legal and ethical complexities surrounding this topic.

The integration of AI tools like ChatGPT and Gemini within education offers a range of benefits and challenges (Rane, 2024). Rane (2024) highlights the potential for AI to streamline content creation, personalize learning experiences, and identify student difficulties. However, concerns exist regarding plagiarism risks and the need for educators to curate and review AI-generated materials. Ensuring responsible and ethical implementation of AI in education is crucial (Rane, 2024).

The decision by Google AI to rebrand from Bard to Gemini raises questions about the impact of naming on AI perception (Rayhan, 2024). Rayhan's (2024) research explores the historical context and potential ramifications of this name change, suggesting that brand choices can influence public perception, industry dynamics, and societal views of AI.

Employee engagement is a crucial aspect of organizational performance. Sari (2020) investigated whether AI-based tools can aid managers in detecting and addressing factors influencing employee engagement. While the study employed a qualitative approach, it highlights the potential for AI to enhance people analytics within organizations (Sari, 2020).

As AI becomes increasingly integrated into communication technologies, user experience becomes critical. Shin et al. (2021) proposed a method for evaluating user satisfaction with voice-based intelligent systems using questionnaires focusing on Kansei words, which represent user emotions and sensitivities. Their findings suggest that factors like the AI's sentence structure and its ability to answer questions correctly influence user satisfaction (Shin et al., 2021). This research contributes to developing methods for understanding user experience with AI chatbots.

The study "AI-Powered Super-Workers" by Valeriya et al. (2024) presents an empirical exploration of AI's impact on workforces. Based on real data, they report significant increases in both employee productivity and satisfaction following AI integration (Valeriya et al., 2024). These findings suggest that AI can enhance worker capabilities and well-being, but further research is required to explore the generalizability and long-term implications of these results.

While AI chatbots are increasingly prevalent, limited research has examined user experience. Xie (2022) conducted a meta-analysis that explored the relationship between user satisfaction with AI chatbots and four dimensions of user gratification: utilitarian, technological, hedonic, and social. Their findings suggest that utilitarian gratification, focusing on the usefulness of the chatbot, has the strongest influence on user satisfaction. This emphasizes the importance of utility-driven design principles for AI chatbots (Xie, 2022).

Research plan

Measures

This study employed the well-established Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWL) developed by Diener et al. (1985) to measure subjective well-being, a widely used concept in various research fields. The five-item questionnaire provided valuable insights for the research by covering a range of topics related to AI tool usage, life satisfaction, and demographic information.

Questionnaire design

A separate 16-item questionnaire was developed to gather additional data:

- Life Satisfaction Rating (Q1): Participants rated their life satisfaction on various aspects using a 7-point Likert scale.
- AI Tool Usage (Q2-Q7):
- Participants indicated whether they had ever used OpenAI ChatGPT (Q2). If yes, they reported the average number of hours per week they used it (Q3).
- Similar questions were asked for Google Bard-Gemini (Q4-Q5) and Bing (Q6-Q7).
- Other AI Tools Usage (Q8): Participants listed any other AI tools they used.
- Purposes of AI Tool Usage (Q9): Participants specified the purposes for which they most frequently used the mentioned AI tools.
- Governmental Perspective on AI Tool Usage (Q10): Participants described what governmental actions or policies would encourage them to use AI tools more.
- Ban on AI Tools in Schools (Q11): Participants expressed their opinion on whether the use of AI tools should be banned in schools.
- Change in Life Satisfaction (Q12): Participants indicated whether their overall life satisfaction had changed since they started using AI tools.
- Demographic Information (Q13-16): Participants provided information on gender (Q13), age (Q14), education level (Q15), and country of residence (Q16).

Data collection

The research was conducted from March 28, 2024, to April 28, 2024. The questionnaire was translated into five languages: Slovenian, English, Serbian, Macedonian, and Russian. Professors and students forwarded the questionnaire to their students and friends. The obtained data was edited in Excel and then analyzed using the IBM SPSS22 software package.

Sample

A total of 1,296 respondents participated in the study. The sample included 424 men (32.7%) and 872 women (67.3%). The average age of the participants was 30.93 years old (SD = 13.4 years). In terms of nationality, 737 were Slovenian, 171 Serbian, 127 from North Macedonia, 63 from Bosnia and Herzegovina, 47 from India, 80 from Russia, and 21 from other countries (Sweden, Spain, Bharat, Kazakhstan, Croatia, USA, Germany, Canada, Finland, Dominican Republic, Belgium, Brazil, and Romania). Regarding education level, 20 participants had completed high school, 605 had a secondary school education, and 117 had completed elementary school or less.

Results – confirmation of hypotheses

Hypothesis:

H1: More than 50% of respondents have used OpenAI ChatGPT.

Table 1: Have you ever used Open AI ChatGPT?

(Own research 2024)

	Frequency	Percent
yes	805	62,1
no	491	37,9
Total	1296	100,0

When examining Hypothesis 1, we found that 805 respondents (62.1%) already use Open ChatGPT, while 471 respondents (37.9%) do not (Table 1). We can confirm hypothesis 1.

H2: More than 50% of respondents have used Gemini.

Table 2: Have you ever used Open Gemini?

(Own research 2024)

	Frequency	Percent
yes	134	10,3
no	1162	89,7
Total	1296	100,0

Upon examining (Table 2) Hypothesis 2, we discovered that 134 respondents (10.3%) already use Google Bard (Gemini), while 1,162 (89.7%) have never used it. Based on these findings, Hypothesis 2 cannot be confirmed.

H3: More than 50% of respondents have used Bing.

Upon examining Hypothesis 3 regarding Bing usage (Table 3), we found that 207 respondents (16%) already use Bing, while 1,089 respondents (84%) have never used it. Therefore, Hypothesis 3 cannot be confirmed either.

Table 3: Have you ever used Bing?

(Own research 2024)

	Frequency	Percent
yes	207	16,0
no	1089	84,0
Total	1296	100,0

H4: More than 50% of respondents using AI tools such as OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini, and Bing experienced improved life satisfaction.

Table 4: Do you believe your overall life satisfaction has changed since you started using artificial intelligence tools (OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini, Bing)?

(Own research 2024)

Yes, for the better	273	32,62%
Yes, for the worse	55	6,57%
It hasn't changed	509	60,81%
Total	837	100%

In Hypothesis 4, we examined whether the lives of respondents who use ChatGPT, Google Bard (Gemini), or Bing for their work have improved (Table 4). We found that 32.62% (273 respondents) reported an improvement in their lives, while 60.81% (509 respondents) indicated no change, and only 6.57% (55 respondents) experienced a negative impact on their lives due to using these AI tools. 459 or 35,4% not response. Therefore, Hypothesis 4 cannot be confirmed, as only 32.62% of respondents experienced a positive impact on their lives.

H5: More than 50% of respondents do not support the ban on the use of artificial intelligence in schools, including tools such as OpenAI ChatGPT, Google Bard-Gemini, and Bing.

Regarding Hypothesis 5, we can conclude that 50.8% (658 respondents) would not prohibit the use of AI tools like ChatGPT, Bard, and Bing in schools. Only 25.5% (331 respondents) would prohibit their use, while 23.7% (307 respondents) are unsure about whether or not they would support a ban (Table 5). We can confirm Hypothesis 5.

Table 5: Would you ban the use of the mentioned artificial intelligence tools in schools?

(Own research 2024)

	Frequency	Percent
yes	331	25,5
no	658	50,8
I don't know	307	23,7
Total	1296	100,0

We also want to answer the question: What governmental actions or policies would incentivize individuals to increase their personal usage of the mentioned artificial intelligence tools? Governments can increase the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) among individuals, categorized with estimated percentages of potential impact:

Education and Awareness (40%)

1. Implement AI education programs in schools: Introduce AI concepts and skills into primary, secondary, and higher education curricula to equip individuals with the knowledge and expertise to navigate the AI-driven world. (20%)
2. Launch public awareness campaigns: Conduct nationwide campaigns to inform the public about the benefits, applications, and potential of AI, dispelling misconceptions and fostering a positive perception of AI. (10%)
3. Promote AI literacy and training opportunities: Provide accessible and affordable AI training programs for individuals of all ages and backgrounds, enabling them to develop practical AI skills for personal and professional use. (10%)

Infrastructure and Accessibility (30%)

1. Invest in AI research and development: Allocate significant funding to support cutting-edge AI research and development, ensuring that the country remains at the forefront of AI innovation. (15%)
2. Develop a robust AI infrastructure: Build a high-speed, reliable, and secure AI infrastructure, including data centers, networks, and cloud computing capabilities, to support the deployment and utilization of AI applications. (10%)
3. Promote open-source AI tools and resources: Encourage the development and sharing of open-source AI tools, libraries, and datasets to democratize access to AI technology and foster innovation. (5%)

Policy and Regulation (20%)

1. Establish clear AI governance frameworks: Develop comprehensive AI governance frameworks that outline ethical guidelines, data privacy standards, and transparency principles to ensure responsible AI development and deployment. (10%)
2. Incentivize AI adoption in businesses: Implement tax breaks, subsidies, and other incentives to encourage businesses of all sizes to adopt AI solutions and integrate them into their operations. (5%)
3. Support AI-driven entrepreneurship: Provide funding, mentorship, and incubation support for AI startups and entrepreneurs, fostering a thriving AI ecosystem. (5%)

Public-Private Partnerships (10%)

1. Foster collaboration between government and industry: Encourage collaboration between government agencies and private sector partners to develop and implement AI solutions that address societal challenges and drive economic growth. (5%)
2. Establish AI research consortia: Facilitate the formation of research consortia bringing together academia, industry, and government to tackle complex AI challenges and accelerate innovation. (5%)

Conclusion

This study investigated the use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools and its impact on life satisfaction. The study also explored public opinion on the use of AI tools in schools.

Key Findings:

- OpenAI ChatGPT was the most widely used AI tool, with over 62% of respondents reporting using it.
- Hypotheses 2 and 3 were not confirmed, as less than 50% of respondents reported using Google Bard (Gemini) or Bing.
- Hypothesis 4 regarding a positive impact on life satisfaction was not confirmed. While some respondents reported improvement, a significant portion reported no change or a negative impact.
- Hypothesis 5 was confirmed. A majority of respondents (over 50%) did not support a ban on AI tools in schools.

Additional Insights:

- A significant number of respondents (over 35%) did not respond to the question about life satisfaction change after using AI tools. This limits the generalizability of the findings for Hypothesis 4.
- The study also identified potential strategies for governments to increase AI adoption, focusing on education, awareness, infrastructure, and policy.

Future Research:

- Further investigation is needed to understand the factors influencing life satisfaction changes after using AI tools.
- Research on the specific impacts of different AI tools on various aspects of life satisfaction would be valuable.
- Exploring the reasons behind public hesitancy towards AI tools and the potential benefits of AI in education could be beneficial.
- Expanding the research to include more countries and comparing the results across these countries would be beneficial.
- Do research on the ethical implications of AI use in daily life.

We are delighted to conduct this research. Thirty authors have indeed worked on it, and we hope that the conclusions will be disseminated to each government and put into practice, encouraging the use of the mentioned AI tools in daily life, not just in schools.

Literature

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